

WELD LINE STRENGTH OF HYBRID HEMP/GF/PP INJECTION MOLDINGS

Tomoko OHTA, Yew Wei LEONG and Hiroyuki HAMADA*

Advanced Fibro Science, Kyoto Institute of Technology, Matsugasaki, Sakyo-ku,
606-8585 Kyoto, JAPAN

*Email: Hhamada1@aol.com

SUMMARY

Hemp and glass fibers were selected as the reinforcement for polypropylene (PP) to form hybrid composites with enhanced mechanical performance and consistency. Fiber orientation due to hybridization will be discussed while the weld line strength of these hybrid composites will be elucidated.

Keywords: Hybrid, natural fiber, weld line, composites, injection molding

METHODOLOGY

Long hemp fiber-PP (hemp/PP) pellets were prepared by using the long fiber pellet pultrusion technique, whereby the fiber bundles were continuously pulled and twisted while an extruder supplies the resin that were fed into a heated die where it impregnates into the fiber bundles. In order to ensure minimal decomposition of the fibers through shear heating, a special high flow PP grade (MFR>500 g/10 mins) was used during this impregnation stage. After sufficient cooling, the impregnated fiber bundles were cut into pellets according to the desired length. In this study, the length of the pellets was 11 mm for the hemp/PP composites, which contain 40 wt% hemp. As for GF/PP composites, normal short fiber pellets containing 30wt% GF were used (Sumitomo Chemicals Co. Ltd.). PP resin pellets (Japan Polypropylene; MFR=30 g/10 mins) were used in order to dilute the contents of both materials. These pellets were injection molded into dumbbell specimens and the material compositions are described in Table 1.

PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Fig.1 shows tensile load-displacement curves for all the specimens. Since all of them are weld line specimens, brittle fracture behavior could be observed. The typical tensile strengths, which indicate the strengths of the welded region for these specimens are

compiled in Fig. 2.

The highest weld line strength was exhibited by the hemp/PP composites (0:100:0) while the weakest weld lines could be found in GF/PP composites (100:0:0). The hybrid specimens, however, experienced an increase in weld line strength with decreasing hemp fiber content. This is a completely different tendency from the monotonic materials system, which could be due to the difference in fiber distribution in hybrid composites as compared to monotonic composites.

Non-weld specimen will be also fabricated and ratio of weld strength to no-weld strength will also be discussed. Furthermore SEM observation will be conducted on tensile fractured surfaces in order to understand the fracture behavior and also fiber orientation states corresponding to the flow pattern of reinforcing fibers during the filling stage of injection molding, especially at the flow front since the weld line is generated through the meeting of these melt fronts.

Table 1: Specimen designation

Specimen Designation	Composite System	GF/PP Pellet Content (wt%)	Hemp/PP Pellet Content (wt%)	PP Pellet Content (wt%)
50:50:0	Hybrid	50	50	0
50:40:10	Hybrid	50	40	10
50:30:20	Hybrid	50	30	20
50:20:30	Hybrid	50	20	30
50:10:40	Hybrid	50	10	40
50:0:50	Monotonic	50	0	50
40:60:0	Hybrid	40	60	0
30:70:0	Hybrid	30	70	0
20:80:0	Hybrid	20	80	0
10:90:0	Hybrid	10	90	0
0:100:0	Monotonic	0	100	0
100:0:0	Monotonic	100	0	0

Figure 1: Load-displacement curves of weld specimen

Figure 2: Weld line strength